

THE IMPORTANCE OF FECAL CALPROTECTIN IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF ANTIBIOTIC-ASSOCIATED DIARRHEA CAUSED BY *CLOSTRIDIUM DIFFICILE* IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. At present time pediatricians, gastroenterologists, infectious disease specialists, and other medical professionals are paying increased attention to antibiotic-associated diarrhea. This is largely due to the widespread, often unprescribed and uncontrolled use of antibacterial drugs, frequently available in pharmacies without a prescription. Such practices contribute to the growing resistance of conditionally pathogenic microorganisms in the body. According to the WHO definition, antibiotic-associated diarrhea is characterized by an increase in stool frequency (more than three times a day) during or within eight weeks after antibiotic therapy. It is often accompanied by an increase in stool volume, changes in consistency, and the appearance of pathological inclusions such as mucus, greenish coloration, and blood [1].

Keywords: *clostridium difficile*, antibiotic-associated diarrhea, children, fecal calprotectin.

Introduction. According to foreign researchers, 11% of antibiotic-associated diarrhea cases in children occur after outpatient antibacterial therapy. These types of diarrheas are most frequently observed in children aged between 2 months and 3 years who have taken antibiotics. Diarrhea is most commonly associated with treatment using amoxicillin/clavulanate (23%), erythromycin (16%), and cephalosporins (9%) [2,3].

According to our data, 54.2% of antibiotic-associated diarrhea cases in children under 3 years of age were caused by *Clostridium difficile*. The most common culprits were third- and fourth-generation cephalosporins (67.5%), followed by aminopenicillins and aminoglycosides (32.3%), and in some cases, first-generation cephalosporins, carbapenems and nitrofurans.

Certainly, in clinical presentation, antibiotic-associated diarrhea caused by *Clostridium difficile* primarily manifests as septic enterocolitis (69%) and post-infectious enterocolitis (38.7%). These conditions are mainly characterized by high body temperature, dehydration, and moderate to severe exsiccosis (fluid loss).

The clinical forms of *Clostridium difficile*-induced antibiotic-associated diarrhea include:

- asymptomatic *Clostridium difficile*-associated enteritis,
- *Clostridium difficile*-associated enterocolitis or colitis,
- and pseudomembranous colitis [4].

The course of *Clostridium difficile*-induced antibiotic-associated diarrhea depends on factors such as the duration of antibacterial therapy, antibiotic resistance, disturbances to the intestinal mucosal microecology, and is influenced by pathomorphological and metabolic changes, as well as inflammatory characteristics [5].

In this regard, to improve diagnostics and accurately assess the degree of intestinal inflammation in children with *Clostridium difficile*-induced antibiotic-associated diarrhea, a new diagnostic indicator is currently being used: the level of calprotectin in feces.

Besides that, fecal calprotectin is considered a specific marker of intestinal inflammation. Calprotectin belongs to a group of calcium-binding proteins and consists of one light and two heavy polypeptide chains, with a total molecular weight of 36.5 kDa. This protein is secreted by neutrophils and possesses bacteriostatic and fungicidal properties [6–7]. Its concentration in blood, synovial fluid, urine, and stool reflects the activity and extent of inflammation and tissue damage.

During inflammation, the concentration of calprotectin in blood plasma can increase by 5 to 40 times [8–9]. In patients with inflammatory bowel diseases, the level of calprotectin in feces increases significantly and can be several times higher than that found in blood plasma. A correlation has also been found between fecal calprotectin concentration and neutrophil release, which confirms its direct association with the activity of inflammation in the colon. This is due to enhanced neutrophil migration through the inflamed intestinal mucosa [10].

In healthy children older than one year, the level of calprotectin in the stool is less than 50 µg/g. However, in newborn infants, its content can be up to 10 times higher than that of older children. This is due to their anatomical and physiological characteristics, such as the structure of the intestinal mucosa, the exposure to various antigens through the gastrointestinal tract, the immaturity of the immune system, and other factors [11].

In addition, the fecal calprotectin level also correlates with the severity of the disease. Fecal calprotectin serves as a marker of intestinal inflammation and has distinct advantages: it is resistant to proteolytic enzymes, remains stable in stool samples at room temperature for up to 7 days, and even a small amount of stool is sufficient to determine its level using the ELISA method—typically around 50 mg is enough [12].

Research Objective: To determine the significance of fecal calprotectin in diagnosing antibiotic-associated diarrhea caused by *Clostridium difficile* in children.

Research Materials and Methods. Our study involved 151 children aged from 1 month to 3 years who were hospitalized in the departments of gastroenterology and pulmonology at the Samarkand Regional Children’s Multidisciplinary Medical Center (Chief Physician: Prof. Azizov M.K.) during 2023–2024.

Results and discussion. All patients included in the study underwent anamnesis collection, clinical-laboratory, and instrumental examinations. According to protocol, patients received the following tests: complete blood count, urinalysis, stool analysis, biochemical tests, bacteriological stool culture, and ELISA and PCR tests of stool samples.

Instrumental examinations included ultrasound (USG), chest and abdominal X-rays, and colonoscopy. To implement the objectives of the scientific research, all patients were divided into 3 groups:

Group I (Main Group): 86 children who had received antibiotic therapy and tested positive for *Clostridium difficile* toxin A or toxin B.

Group II (Comparison Group): 38 children who had received antibiotic therapy and developed diarrhea but tested negative for *Clostridium difficile*.

Group III (Control Group): 27 children who had received antibiotic therapy but did not develop diarrhea.

In our study, when analyzing the total number of children based on gender, it was found that 93 patients (62%) were boys and 58 (38%) were girls. This indicates a higher frequency of occurrence in boys.

Gender distribution of the total number of children

In both groups, stool samples from the patients were tested for fecal calprotectin using the ELISA method, and the results were evaluated. According to the findings, the highest level of fecal calprotectin in the main group was 702.3 $\mu\text{g/g}$, while in the comparison group, this figure was 247.7 $\mu\text{g/g}$.

While analyzing the diagnoses within the main group, septic enterocolitis accounted for 47.8% of the cases, and post-infectious enterocolitis made up 38.6%.

Conclusion. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that children in the main group (those who tested positive for *C. difficile*) had a significantly higher degree of intestinal inflammation. Therefore, determining fecal calprotectin levels plays an important role in diagnosing antibiotic-associated diarrhea caused by *Clostridium difficile*.

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